

Deliverable D-JRP22-WP5.1

Workpackage 5

Responsible Partner: ISS

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP22-WP5.1 Data Management Plan		
Project Acronym	MEME		
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Other contributors	MEME consortium		
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Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>	
	National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>		
	EFSA <input type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other	international	stakeholder(s):
		
	Social Media:		
	Other recipient(s):		

MEME DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Aim and focus, specific considerations

Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element of data management during a project. It covers the life cycle of the data from collection to availability and long-term storage. MEME DMP is a living document that will cover the relevant aspects of the many types of data that are collected and generated during the project. MEME will do its best to make the research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. Ethical considerations, GDPR, data security and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are considered along the process. In addition to the components of the FAIR-principle, transparency and visibility are also emphasized.

1.1. Process and format

The list of data covered in MEME DMP is specified and updated during the project, and management of the data is discussed proactively. MEME DMP is updated on yearly base. DMP is regularly discussed with the MEME-WP-leaders and with the MEME Consortium during the project.

1.2. Resources

MEME Project Leader is responsible of the MEME DMP and has allocated time for developing, compiling and updating it. MEME Project Leader participates in DMP Committee of the OHEJP. Resources have been earmarked for publishing Gold open access.

1.3. Example of data covered by MEME DMP:

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the MEME DMP interface. The browser tabs include 'Validation of PCR...', 'Comparison of T...', 'Zenodo', 'Edibleable D-RP-TO...', 'TOXOSOURCES...', 'One Health EP...', 'RD Web Access...', 'Lisam ComplyStation', and 'Lisam ComplyStation'. The address bar shows 'https://apps.isam.com/apps/CDP'. The page title is 'Lisam ComplyStation'. The main content area shows a table titled 'View MEME - Data Management - Records overview'. The table has columns: Dataset ID, Category, Type of data, Species, Matrix, Description, Contact, Dissemin..., and Sustainability. The table contains 16 rows of data, each with a checkbox in the first column and a '1' in the last column. The table is paginated, showing 'Page 1 of 2' and 'View 1 - 15 of 16'.

Dataset ID	Category	Type of data	Species	Matrix	Description	Contact	Dissemin...	Sustainability
JRP-18-COLLECTION_OF_SAMPLES_IN_THE_FIELD	Research data	Biological collection	Not rele...	Other	JRP-18-COLLE..._j.karamon...	Scientific p...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-COLLECTION_OF_SAMPLES_FROM_EXPERIMENTAL_ANIMAL_MODEL	Research data	Biological collection	Sheep	Serum	JRP-18-COLLE..._adriano.ca...	Scientific p...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-NEW_MOLECULAR_MARKERS	Research data	Molecular collection	Not rele...	Organs	JRP-18-NEW..._Gerald.L.M...	Mfrod. S. O...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-NEW_MULTIPLEX_TAQMAN_QPCR	Research data	Molecular collection	Not rele...	Organs	JRP-18-NEW..._Pavlo.Maks...	Maksimov ...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-POTENTIAL_BIOMARKERS_FOR_INTERMEDIATE_HOSTS_PLASMA	Research data	Molecular collection	Sheep	Serum	JRP-18-POTEN..._adriano.ca...	scientific p...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-CONTAMINATION_OF_VEGETABLES_BY_EM_EG	Research data	Surveillance output	Not rele...	Other	JRP-18-CONTA..._gerald.umh...	scientific p...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-PREVALENCE_OF_EM_EG_IN_DOGS_FROM_SELECTED_GEOGRAPHICAL_AREAS	Research data	Surveillance output	Dog	Faeces	PREVALENCE..._j.karamon...	scientific p...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-POTENTIAL_HUMAN_RISK_FACTORS_BY_MEANS_OF_QUESTIIONAIRES	Research data	Questionnaires	Human	Not relevant	JRP-18-POTEN..._adriano.ca...	Casulli, A. L...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-EG_GENOTYPE_DIVERSITY_IN_SELECTED_AREAS	Research data	Molecular collection	Not rele...	Organs	JRP-18-EG_G..._adriano.ca...	scientific p...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-SOPS_FOR_SAMPLING_IN_MATRICES	Methodologies	Methods	Not rele...	Other	JRP-18-SOPS..._adriano.ca...	Internation...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-ASSESSMENT_OF_NEWLY_DEVELOPED_METHODS_AGAINST_THE_EXISTING	Methodologies	Methods	Not rele...	Other	JRP-18-ASSE..._Pavlo.Maks...	Borelli, R. ...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-NEW_NGS_METHOD_FOR_THE_DETECTION_IN_COMPLEX_SAMPLES	Methodologies	Methods	Not rele...	Faeces	JRP-18-NEW..._shivind.ome...	scientific p...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-VALIDATION_OF_SISCT	Methodologies	Methods	Wild ani...	Other	JRP-18-VALIDA..._gerald.umh...	Internation...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-VALIDATION_OF_MULTIPLE_PCERS	Methodologies	Methods	Not rele...	Other	JRP-18-VALIDA..._adriano.ca...	Santolama...	31 Dec 2022	1
JRP-18-VALIDATION_OF_MAGNETIC_CAPTURE_REAL_TIME_PCR_ASSAY	Methodologies	Methods	Not rele...	Faeces	JRP-18-VALIDA..._mattis.saks...	Internation...	31 Dec 2022	1